

PROLIFICATION IN A DOUBLE-FLOWERED FORM OF CALENDULA OFFICINALIS

Extremely Rare Development of Multiple Buds in Pot Marigold

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PROLIFICATION is a word often used by horticulturists to denote a departure from the ordinary method of flowering of cultivated plants. It is used generally where more flower buds are produced than is commonly the rule, and especially so when they appear where ordinarily they would not, as in the present instance, where a number of flower buds were developed from one normal flower head.

Although proliferation is not uncommon in some double-flowered plants, the writer has never before seen this occurrence in the *Calendula*.

These plants were grown in the spring of 1918, at Twin Oaks, Washington, D. C., by Mr. E. G. Anderson, who is superintendent for Mr. Charles J. Bell. My attention was attracted to the strange behavior of several of the flowers; the central flower was apparently normal, but before it was fully developed several buds were produced—some from the center of the flower (see Fig. 12). These developed into flowers and opened fully, although not as large as the first; these later, in several instances again produced buds that developed flowers, they, in turn, not as large as the second tier (Fig. 13).

I left at about this time for the

West and therefore did not see the final stages of these flowers, but asked Mr. Anderson to save any seed that might mature so that we could try another experiment to determine if this proliferation would become fixed. Unfortunately no seed developed, and the plants, being annuals, were necessarily lost.

This form of proliferation often occurs in the double-flowered English daisy, and in England has received the common and expressive name of the Hen-and-Chicken Daisy. Proliferation also frequently occurs among our common roses. In the rose, however, it often takes the form of the prolonged flower stalk coming up from the center of the parent flower, often producing leaves and then a bud which develops later into a flower.

The *Calendula* plants, here shown, were grown in a greenhouse bench in rather rich soil and where they were given the best of care as regards watering, temperature, fertilization, etc.—in fact, ideal conditions for the best development of normal flowers. It might be asked, were the conditions conducive to the production of such prolific flowers as were borne by several of the plants. I am inclined to think that this was the case, and that they were over-stimulated.

POT MARIGOLD PROLIFICATION

Pot marigold (*Calendula officinalis*), showing the flower head, with buds and flowers. Many flower buds are in the course of development in the central or main flower, and can be seen in the illustration. (Fig. 12.)

POT MARIGOLD PROLIFICATION

Pot marigold (*Calendula officinalis*) showing the flower proliferation further developed. The outer or secondary flowers shown here produced later other tiers of flowers not shown in the illustration. (Fig. 13.)